

CELLULOSE NANOCOMPOSITES WITH DUCTILE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR

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ABSTRACT

The limited ductility of plant fiber biocomposites is typically caused by interfacial debonding mechanisms at low strain. This leads to damage development and premature failure. The present paper discusses recent results on cellulose nanocomposites with thermoset and thermoplastic matrices, where substantial ductility is observed. The data are presented and reasons for the observed ductility are discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Although plant fiber biocomposites with polymer matrices are used in load-bearing applications in the automotive, building and packaging industries, the use could be expanded provided the mechanical performance was improved. In particular, problems with moisture sensitivity and lack of ductility are substantial. The limited strain to failure is often related to interfacial debonding between fiber and matrix at low strain. The fiber/matrix adhesion may be limited to start with if the chemical interaction between the phases is unfavorable. Variations in local moisture content could worsen the situation and even cause complete debonding. Nanocomposites based on cellulose nanofibers (CNF) are of great interest in this context since they may offer a number of advantages. CNF has the potential to become a widely used nanofiber of low cost due to its wood pulp origin. The moisture-induced swelling of the nanofibers is much more limited than in plant fibers of heterogeneous composition. Typical dimensions of recent CNF are 3-15 nm in diameter and 0.7-3 micrometers in length. The CNF tend to be swirled and very flexible, perhaps partly due to some imperfections in the crystallites induced during disintegration from the pulp fibers. CNF composites with polymer matrices can be prepared by filtration of CNF from hydrocolloidal suspensions so that a porous CNF network with random-in-the-plane CNF orientation is formed, and subsequent impregnation by unsaturated polyester (UP) or epoxy (EP) precursors followed by curing. It is also possible to coat individual CNF:s with a water-soluble polymer matrix and simply allow a filtrated wet "cake" to dry and form a nanocomposite film. Preparation, structure and properties of the biocomposites are discussed, with special emphasis on strategies for materials design in order to achieve ductile material behavior.

2 PREPARATION OF CELLULOSE NANOFIBER (CNF) MATS

Although the nature of the CNF themselves will not be discussed in detail, it is sufficient to state that it is essential to ensure that the lateral diameter of the CNF is sufficiently small. Large nanofiber diameters (ie 40 nm) are agglomerates of smaller fibrils and may be sites for failure initiation during mechanical loading. CNF with preserved surface chemistry as in nature typically have average diameters around 6 nm.

A procedure to prepare CNF mats is illustrated in Figure 1. A hydrocolloidal suspension of CNFs dispersed in water is subjected to filtration, in much the same way as papermaking is carried out industrially (although as a continuous process). A wet cake is formed on the permeable membrane, and typically the solid content is around 30wt% after filtration. The CNF aspect ratio (ratio of length to diameter) can typically be around 100. The orientation distribution of CNF is normally random-in-the-plane with some limited out-of-plane CNF orientation. The porosity of the network will depend on the

drying conditions of the film, but is often 10-20% and much lower than for typical paper structures.

Figure 1: Preparation procedure for cellulose nanofiber mats by filtration and drying of colloidal suspensions of CNF nanofibers.

3 CHARACTERISTICS OF CELLULOSE NANOFIBER (CNF) MATS

The strongest nanofiber mat structures also tend to be the most ductile [1]. They have high cellulose molar mass, which should have a positive effect on tensile strength. The “best” CNF have carboxylate groups on the topochemically modified CNF fibrils. Testing is carried out at conditions of 50% relative humidity (RH). One may speculate that fibrils with carboxylate functionality in the suspension become hydrated on the surface in the nanopaper form. This could favor plastic deformation since the hydrated region may serve as a lubricant and thus facilitate the sliding of fibrils with respect to each other.

New drying methods have been used for CNF aerogels and nanopaper structures [2, 3]. Very porous aerogels were prepared by solvent exchange from water to tert-butanol followed by drying [3]. This resulted in much higher specific surface area (SSA) of the aerogels (150-280 m²/g) compared with freeze-dried aerogels prepared from water. The resulting aerogels showed a fine CNF network structure and much lower modulus and yield strength compared with freeze-dried foams with cellular structure. Fitting of modulus data to a theoretical fiber network model resulted in estimated CNF segment lengths of 300-480 nm between CNF-CNF joints, in agreement with structures observed in FE-SEM microscopy.

CNF nanopaper structures have also been dried by several different methods [2]. Stress-strain curves for such CNF nanopaper structures of high specific surface area show high ductility. Drying from supercritical carbon dioxide results in an SSA of 480 m²/g. The strain to failure of this “SC-CO₂” nanopaper is 17% at 56% porosity and 50% RH. The modulus is 1.4 GPa (quite low) and the strength in tension is 84 MPa. In a fiber network model context, we may relate higher specific surface area to increased fiber segment length between CNF-CNF joints. This explains lowered modulus and yield strength. The increased strain to failure indicates that CNF fibril sliding and reorientation with respect to neighboring fibrils is facilitated.

4 DUCTILE POLYMER MATRIX NANOCOMPOSITES FROM CNF

CNF nanopaper or “mats” are unique and can be utilized in polymer matrix nanocomposites. It is clear that the mechanisms for plastic deformation in the CNF network (CNF straightening, reorientation, sliding etc) are unlikely in high T_g resin composites of high yield stress.

Svagan et al combined CNF with a thermoplastic starch matrix [4]. The composition was a highly plasticized 50/50 mixture of amylopectin-rich potato starch and glycerol. This polymer is almost

viscous at room temperature due to the plasticizing effect of the glycerol. The highly hydrated primary plant cell wall was an inspiration since it has good mechanical function despite the high water content. The cellulose microfibril network provides the major mechanical function in the plant cell wall. In the bioinspired CNF/starch materials, a modulus of 6.2 GPa, a tensile strength as high as 160 MPa, and a strain-to-failure of 8.1% were observed at 70wt % of CNF reinforcement. The work of fracture (area under stress-strain curve) was as high as 9.4 MJ/m³. An important reason for this unique combination of strength and strain-to-failure in a viscous matrix composite is the nanoscale network structure of the CNF.

Thermoplastic starch is of industrial importance, but cellulose derivatives may also be used to prepare CNF nanocomposites, with a more favorable combination of properties. Cellulose derivatives are synthesized by dissolution of cellulose followed by chemical reactions. The glucose rings in the main chain are given new functionalities and are usually unable to crystallize so that cast films are amorphous. The cellulose backbone and high molar mass provide attractive film properties and yet the polymers are water-soluble. Hydroxyethylcellulose (HEC) was first combined with bacterial cellulose (BC) during BC biosynthesis in an CNF/HEC weight ratio of 80/20 [5]. The resulting composite showed a modulus of 12.5 GPa, yield strength of around 100 MPa, ultimate tensile strength of 290 MPa, strain-to-failure of about 6% and work of fracture 11 MJ/m³. These data are high values, and the HEC was distributed as a coating around the individual BC fibrils. This highly controlled way of HEC distribution is supported by NMR and TEM data in the study. The data for strain to failure (6%) indicate that BC fibril sliding can take place in this HEC matrix material, most likely due to the low yield stress of HEC and its nanoscale distribution as a fibril coating. Later, HEC was combined with CNF from wood in a papermaking type of process [6]. HEC adsorbs to CNF and very little HEC is lost during filtration. Since the HEC content is fairly high, some HEC is adsorbed to CNF fibrils but there are also HEC-rich regions between CNF-rich “flocs”. Results from tensile tests are presented in Figure 2. The 45/41 material has 45 volume percent CNF, 41 percent HEC and an estimated porosity of 14%. The mechanical properties are high, see also Table 1.

The concept of HEC-coated CNF fibrils was also used to prepare nonwoven nanopaper networks [7]. For nonwovens with a porosity of 44%, the nominal strain to failure was 55%, see Table 1. The fibril-fibril interaction is expected to be very low in this high specific surface area material. Again, this example shows the potential to tailor modulus, strength and toughness of nonwoven nanopaper structures. Not only the porosity but also the density and strength of fibril-fibril bonds are important structural parameters to control in the development of such materials.

Figure 2: Stress-strain curves for CNF/HEC nanocomposites prepared by vacuum filtering from CNF suspension containing dissolved HEC, which largely adsorbs to CNF. 45/41 means 45 vol% CNF and 41% HEC estimated from the nanocomposite density, component weight fractions and component densities. 100 minus volume fraction of CNF and HEC is the estimated porosity (14% for 45/41 CNF/HEC). Image from ref [6], reproduced by permission of the Royal Society of Chemistry.

5 THE POTENTIAL OF CNF NANOCOMPOSITES

Molded biocomposites based on plant fibers are often quite brittle and show limited modulus and strength. Biocomposites with improved performance are therefore of great interest. Low strain to failure (<3-4%) is caused by fracture initiation at fiber/matrix interfaces or in agglomerates of large particles. Limitations in modulus (<7GPa) and strength (<100MPa) are related to short aspect ratio of the reinforcement phase and low content of reinforcement (typically <30 percent by volume).

Data for CNF nanopaper and CNF polymer matrix nanocomposites are therefore summarized in Table 1. Data are discussed from top to bottom. Porous CNF nanopaper has a modulus of 13 GPa, a tensile strength of 220 MPa and a strain to failure approaching 10%. With lower porosity the strength can be even higher. The nanopaper shows plastic yielding and then reaches its ultimate strength through substantial strain-hardening. The porous nanopaper network can be used as reinforcement for polymer matrix nanocomposites. The second CNF nanopaper material in Table 1, is more porous and prepared by drying from supercritical CO₂. This nanopaper has higher porosity, weaker fibril-fibril bonds and therefore deforms to a higher strain to failure (17%).

Highly plasticized thermoplastic starch was also used [4] and a favorable effect of this low yield stress matrix was observed on strain to failure. CNF could reorient and slide so that a strain to failure of 8-25% was obtained, depending on CNF content. However, the high glycerol content limits the tensile strength.

The next three materials in Table 1 all have HEC matrix (hydroxy ethyl cellulose). This is a linear, water-soluble high molar mass polymer (cellulose derivative) with high modulus but low yield stress in film form. In mixtures with cellulose fibrils in water, individual HEC molecules adsorb to cellulose surfaces, and the fibrils become coated by a thin HEC layer. Good nanostructural control of the polymer matrix distribution is obtained. Each fibril is compartmentalized by the polymer coating. For the bacterial cellulose (BC) we obtain very high tensile strength (290 MPa). The approach is then

extended to CNF and the volume fraction of HEC is increased. The strain to failure then becomes as high as 26% with a good combination of modulus, strength and toughness. A non-woven material of HEC-coated CNF reaches 55% strain. Again, the reason is that the weakly connected CNF fibrils can reorient and slide to allow large deformation. The “new”, more oriented, CNF structure also results in reasonably high strength (94MPa).

Thermoset composites can also show high ductility combined with high ultimate strength [8], see CNF/EP and CNF/UP towards the bottom of Table 1. The thermoset matrix needs low yield stress in order to provide strain to failure as high as 7-8 %, and strengths around 160-170 MPa. Recently, it was demonstrated that core-shell nanofibers based on amylopectin starch can be used to prepare high volume fraction (Vf) composites (75 vol% CNF) [9]. The flexible nature of CNF mats and the starch coating of the CNF makes this high Vf possible although the mat is random-in-the-plane. The strength is 220 MPa combined with a strain to failure of 8%, see bottom of Table 1.

Composite	CNF content (% by volume)	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	Strain- to-failure (%)	Reference
CNF Nanopaper	80 20% pores	13	220	10	Henriksson et al [1]
CNF Nanopaper (supercritical CO ₂ - drying)	44 56% pores	1.4	84	17	Sehaqui et al [2]
CNF/50-50 starch- glycerol	10-70wt%	0.2-6.2	5-160	8-25	Svagan et al [4]
BC/HEC	80/20	12.5	290	6	Zhou et al [5]
CNF/HEC	45/41 14% pores	7.5	180	26	Sehaqui et al [6]
CNF/HEC nonwoven	20/46 44% pores	1.3	94	55	Sehaqui et al [7]
CNF/EP	50/50	9.8	162	8.4	Ansari et al [8]
CNF/UP	45/55	8.5	173	7.8	Ansari et al (unpublished)
CNF/starch	75/25	13.6	221	8	Prakobna et al [9]

Table 1. Comparison of mechanical properties from tensile tests measured for different types of materials based on CNF (cellulose nanofibers) or BC (bacterial cellulose). HEC = hydroxyethyl cellulose polymer, EP = epoxy (DGEBA/Jeffamine 400), UP = unsaturated polyester.

6 CONCLUSIONS

CNF nanofibers can be combined with low yield stress polymers such as HEC to form cellulose biocomposites with a unique combination of high strength, modulus and strain to failure. The plastic deformation mechanisms in such materials have been discussed. Compared with plant fiber composites, interfacial debonding is suppressed so that highly ductile materials can be obtained due to the nanostructural features of the CNF. Papermaking type of processes can be used and materials with high volume fraction of the reinforcement phase can be formed. As much as 75% by volume of CNF can be used in combination with starch, resulting in an ultimate strength of 220 MPa at 8% strain. Also conventional epoxy thermoset resins of low yield stress can be used, combining strengths up to 160 MPa with a modulus of 10 GPa and a strain to failure of 8% at a cellulose nanofiber content of Vf=0.5.

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